

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D1.7 COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITY REPORT VERSION 3

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Abstract	The deliverable provides an overview of the community building activities the STADIEM consortium organised or participated in during year 3 (October 2022-September 2023) of the project. It relates to D1.1 (Community Building Strategy), D1.4 (Community map and database v3) and builds upon D1.6 (Community building
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	activity report v2) that describes the activities for year 2. This deliverable details for each group of stakeholders the community building activity in accordance with their level of engagement towards STADIEM: 1) inform, 2) convince and 3) engage. It presents in the conclusion some operational lessons learned as well as, based on the results from the previous chapter, some final remarks about community engagement within a STADIEM context (2020-2023).
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CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to STADIEM project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

STADIEM is the first pan-European accelerator and start-up-to-corporate supplier program focusing on scaling of NGM (Next Generation Media) solutions through a co-creation and piloting program between innovative start-ups/scale-ups and European (media) corporates. Given this objective, it will be crucial for the program's success to rely not only on the establishment of a well-functioning community of its four hubs (NMA, VRT, STK, MCB), but also to make fruitful connections with other relevant ecosystems and actors in the EU in order to generate a cross-fertilization. STADIEM can benefit from experiences, stakeholders and benefits from other hubs and networks, while these actors in return can learn from the activities, experiences and best practices from the STADIEM program and projects.

This report provides an overview of the community building activities that the STADIEM consortium organized or participated in during the third and final year of the project, from October 2022 to September 2023.

These activities were based on the Community Building Strategy (see D1.1) and the Community Map and Database (see D1.2 v1, see D1.3v2) and builds further on the focus and related concrete challenges defined in the previous community building activities report in September 2022 (see D1.6 v2).

The community building strategy builds upon three types of stakeholders:

- Stakeholders who need to be informed about the project: cultural/artistic organisations, sectors/verticals unrelated to the media industry, standardisation bodies/initiatives, users/audience/civil society, and public authorities/regulators/policy makers.
- Stakeholders who need to be convinced of the value of the project and contribute to it in specific ways; non-media sectors/verticals related to the media industry, media producers, traditional media, operators, and researchers in industry and academia/education.
- And stakeholders who need to be actively engaged in the project activities: tech innovators, incubators and accelerators, investors, corporates, and start-ups, scale-ups, and SMEs in media tech.

The report shows that STADIEM met almost all the KPIs to measure the success of its community building activities. The first group (inform) was reached mainly through communication and dissemination actions by the project and consortium partners, while the second (convince) and third groups (engage) were reached through targeted communication, encounters, and events of various sizes and formats to build the STADIEM ecosystem and engage them in the STADIEM community.

The main achievements of the third and final project year are the following:

- Deepening 5 key achievements of the previous year:
 - Further increasing the communication output and reach, not only via the STADIEM consortium channels but also via the channels of the hubs and partners.
 - Increase the diversity of formats in print and video in order to show 'behind the scenes' aspect of the program and to provide key outputs about the project to stakeholders .

- Keep a high level of targeted publications via newsletters from STADIEM and specific contributions about STADIEM on partners own channels (social media posts, Tech-I magazine EBU, etc).
 - Increase the STADIEM presence at physical events, both with STADIEM related events or generating word-of-mouth via participation in events.
 - Sustaining a good geographical spread of STADIEM presence across Europe
- Organizing 3 workshops around Europe to present project results to specific target audiences (PTS - Geneva in January 2023 for media corporates/ Latitude59 in May 2023 for investors and scale-ups and Brussels policy workshop in September 2023 for policy makers).
 - Setting up 3 specific events to connect STADIEM beneficiaries with target groups (investors and growth and scaling experts): STADIEM Investor Week (Slush 2022 and Big Score 2022) - Bandcamp Storytek – match event at MediaTechFestival Media City Odense.
 - Organizing a series of 5 formal showcasing and 2 informal networking events around Europe - PTS 2023, DTS 2023, Latitude59, Media City Odense MediaTech Festival, Future Week 2022, IBC2023.
 - STADIEM showcasing or networking events took not only place at conferences hosted by project partners (e.g., Future Week at MCB, PTS at EBU) but increasingly made use of the partners network to organise events at other important international business events to connect the project and its beneficiaries with local and various international ecosystems (Slush, Big Score, OMR, TechChill Milano, Media City Odense, etc).

Looking back at the results for the whole duration of the project (September 2020- September 2023), three major conclusions can be drawn:

- On the level of the KPI's, almost all have been met every year and the initial strategy did not have to change significantly. Lower performance at the beginning of the project on some KPIs compared to the final year was due to the Covid19 situation in Europe, although online events and alternatives to conferences were set up and attended in the first 18 months of STADIEM. The score regarding followers on the social media channels of STADIEM is understandable given the chosen approach of STADIEM to also leverage the communication on partners channels, which was done on a regular manner by the partners and especially the 4 hubs. Nonetheless, STADIEM managed to increase every year the followers its accounts (as well as partners account due to STADIEM).
- The community building activities need a good online and offline interaction. Physical international events are important to reach out to and inform key players from the ecosystem, get new contacts, or deepen existing relations during meetings at STADIEM boots. Online actions merely serve information and recall purposes.
- The actions served the focus area of community building activities during the different stages of the project: in the first 18 months a focus on recruiting actors for the different dimensions of the program (scale-ups for the program, experts for framework building, support and trainings) was the key focus; from the summer of 2022 onwards activities served more showcasing purposes and convincing stakeholders from the convince, inform and engage segments to inform and support the sustainability work.

The STADIEM consortium has managed to create and maintain a broader ecosystem around its start-up to corporate supplier accelerator program. The community map (see D1.5v3), a database of contacts and partners that were engaged during the project lifespan, underpins this claim. The strategy to keep this ecosystem community alive after the project is related to both the short term and long-term actions described in the sustainability plan. It will be important that on the short term via the STADIEM channels

updates, if available, about a new cycle of STADIEM will be announced. The project partners will play an important role as well by using their network, contacts, events and communication channels to inform the various STADIEM stakeholders from the established ecosystem about new initiatives, to involve them elaboration of the future STADIEM plans and scenarios but also to reach out to them for more local hub-based initiatives where STADIEM experiences and learnings are integrated in programs with start-ups and scale-ups.

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ABBREVIATIONS

- **MCB:** Media City Bergen, project partner
- **VRT :** Vlaamse Radio en Televisieomroep, project partner
- **STK:** Storytek, project partner
- **NMA:** Next Media Accelerator, project partner
- **EBU:** European Broadcasting Union, project partner
- **F6S:** project partner
- **MAR:** Martel, project partner
- **OC1:** Open Call 1, referring to the first cycle of the STADIEM Innovation Program that had two cycles with two cohorts (May 2021- September 2022)
- **OC2:** Open Call 2, referring to the first cycle of the STADIEM Innovation Program that had two cycles with two cohorts (May 2022-September 2023)

1. INTRODUCTION

This document presents an overview of the community building activities that the STADIEM consortium organised or participated in during the third and final year of the project (October 2022 to September 2023). These activities are based on the tasks T1.1 "Community Building Strategy", T1.2 "Ecosystem Mapping" and T1.3 "Opportunity Spotting" carried out during this time. The report is based on the conclusions of the Deliverable D1.5 "Community Building Activity Report v2", which covered the STADIEM community building activities for the second year of the project (October 2021 to September 2022). The main outcome of that report was that there was no need to update the initial community building strategy outlined in D1.1 "Community Building Strategy".

The report is structured into five chapters:

- Chapter 2 provides the key elements of the community building strategy as background information to understand the overview of the activities and monitoring in the third year of STADIEM.
- Chapters 3, 4, and 5 provide an overview of the activities for each of the three stakeholder groups identified by their level of engagement: 'Inform' (Chapter 3), 'Convince' (Chapter 4), and 'Engage' (Chapter 5).
- Based on a monitoring of the activities compared to the KPIs set for each of these three groups, the report concludes in Chapter 6 with the main insights for the final year, a look towards the future and some general lessons learned about community building during the STADIEM project.

Finally, the Annexes section includes for the 3rd project year a list of videos, social media posts (LinkedIn, X/Twitter, Instagram) by partners, and targeted publications by the consortium, as well as the links to check out these posts and publications online.

2. KEY ELEMENTS OF STADIEM'S COMMUNITY BUILDING STRATEGY

• Main groups of Stakeholders

The STADIEM project has identified three main groups of stakeholders in its ecosystem: inform, convince, and engage.

Each group has a specific value for the STADIEM project and can also benefit from STADIEM activities and outcomes. Also, each group requires a specific level of engagement and specific tactics for engagement.

- The 'Inform' group consists of cultural/artistic organisations, sectors/verticals unrelated to the media industry, standardisation bodies/initiatives, users/audience/civil society, and public authorities/regulators/policy makers.
- The 'Convince' group consists of non-media sectors/verticals related to the media industry, media producers, traditional media, operators, and researchers in industry and academia/education.
- The 'Engage' group consists of tech innovators, incubators and accelerators, investors, corporates, and start-ups, scale-ups, and SMEs in media tech.

Detailed information about these stakeholders can be found in D1.3 "Community Map and Database v2" and its update D1.5 "Community Map and Database v3".

While there is an emphasis that certain community building activities are more appropriate for certain categories, the effects, benefits, and usefulness of such an activity is not meant to be exclusive for that segment. For example, a message on social media can inform wider stakeholders (e.g., another tech vertical) about STADIEM outcomes but has of course also informative value for stakeholders that are more engaged in the project (e.g., a media corporate looking for innovative solutions).

• Release of Covid-19 restriction measures and balance online and offline presence

The STADIEM project's community building activities have been affected by Covid-19 restrictions in Europe during the first and second year of the project. Physical events were deemed unfeasible or cancelled. This final year was the first year where such restrictions were not present anymore. Although STADIEM had prepared for a future where digital and physical events would exist next to each other, we saw that the world returned to the former again and the initial trend identified at the end of the 2nd year was further continued. A combination of online and physical presence, depending on the right context and ambitions to achieve, was therefore the basis for the community activities built in the final year. STADIEM thus deployed a strategy that on the one hand used digital means to inform stakeholders about project developments and make initial connections but used on the other hand physical encounters via workshops, showcases, events and informal gatherings to network and convince stakeholders, generate word-of-mouth effects and offer opportunities for scale-ups to generate business leads. In this way, two-way exchange between the program and project and the ecosystem can take place, leading to a more dynamic and interactive community.

Focus area for community building activities in the final project year.

The focus in community building activities shifted in the last and final year of STADIEM. From building its ecosystem and encouraging media companies and corporates to participate in the STADIEM Innovation Program through the open call process in the first two years, STADIEM now focused on showcasing the results and lessons learned from the program, highlighting

success stories and the life of the scale-ups, and connecting the beneficiaries with relevant stakeholders and audiences to support their continued development after the end of EU funding. STADIEM will continue to use the KPIs defined in its initial community building plan, but the specific events, publications, and social media activities will be tailored to the need to connect with stakeholders that are important for the sustainability of the project.

To support the sustainability of the project after September 2023, STADIEM had set itself the following concrete ambitions in September 2022 (see D1.6 “*Community building activity report v2*”):

- Organize 3 workshops focused each on a certain type of stakeholders to present insights and lessons from the second year of the project and highlight success stories.
 - Set up events and activities to connect STADIEM beneficiaries with relevant actors in the broader ecosystem to support their growth and development.
 - Find and secure a suitable opportunity for the final demo day for the 4 STADIEM OC2 pilots.
 - Develop a strategy for post-project ecosystem engagement and for directing the project's efforts after the end of EU funding.
-
- **Assessing performance and KPI's**

STADIEM uses **the traffic light model** to monitor the extent to which a KPI is reached within the second year of the project. The same interpretation as for the previous reports were used in this report.

KPI met or exceeded
Slightly underperforming
Underperforming /Covid-19 impact

3. INFORM

To inform various stakeholders about the STADIEM project and create awareness about it in wider circles than only the convince and engage segment, the appropriate outreach strategy was discussed and defined between WP1 'Community Building' and WP5 'Outreach and impact creation'. The concrete production of the main communication activities relevant for WP1 purposes (e.g., social media posts) were carried out in WP5 and led by T5.1 Outreach task leader Martel Innovate.

Within the aim of WP1 to build and maintain a community around STADIEM and the particular focus in year 3 to support the message of relevance of STADIEM to support the project's sustainability, the content topics of broader project communication was to talk about results and outcomes of the program and the impact of the accelerator program.

■ 3.1 Detailed look on activities and results in year 3

On a general level, Table 2 shows that in the 3rd and final project year the trends from the previous year were continued: increasing the online communication output, diversifying the communication channels via partners and attending various international network events to generate word-of-mouth effects about STADIEM. In that sense, the STADIEM project addressed the challenge to be more online and offline when it comes to informing its stakeholders and creating opportunities for other stakeholders to contact STADIEM.

The website and social media accounts of the project (Twitter/X and LinkedIn) reached the KPIs that were set (LinkedIn) or almost reached them (Twitter/X). In both cases a steady growth of followers compared to the 2nd year is noted (LinkedIn: +120/Twitter: +40). The four STADIEM hubs used their own channels, beyond resharing (and hence amplifying) the STADIEM posts on the STADIEM social media accounts, to actively communicate about the project, often in relationship to specific STADIEM events in their ecosystem or about the work of the scale-ups in the 2nd cohort for which they were the mother hub. This resharing and active usage of partners channels to communicate about STADIEM can explain the numbers with respect to followers on Twitter and LinkedIn. The same can be said for the rather low view of videos on the STADIEM YouTube channel since they were also reshared by the STADIEM partner channels or posted in another separate post by project partners (see Annex I for an overview on videos and Annex II for an overview of social media posts by partners). The number of impressions for the videos on both LinkedIn and Twitter indicates a growth and a reach of 306K over the three years (+6000K compared to the final year) and hence possible effect of these partner's initiatives on top of Martel Innovate's effort.

Regarding videos, following the advice from STADIEM's Advisory Board in August 2022, the choice was made to diversify the content and formats. While testimonies of participating hubs and scale-ups about the value of the program were gathered during the OC1 batch, for the OC2 batch the focus was put on the interactions that scale-ups had with investors and media corporates (e.g., Investors Week series), on portraying ambitions of scale-ups (Lightning Round and Elevator Pitch) and - via partners' videos - the products that STADIEM scale-ups generated during the program. These videos thus had to inform the stakeholders concretely about what the program does, how it provides for innovators direct access to relevant people in the industry and support to scale. At STADIEM events (see convince and engage section) these videos were re-used in a compilation that served as a dynamic background for the STADIEM boot or pod: these compilations trigger the attention of the visitors and help to illustrate a methodology and approach of STADIEM as an accelerator programme.

Besides providing online information via different channels and formats, another important leverage to reach out to stakeholders is the generation of word-of-mouth about STADIEM

during events. These actions allow to quickly update stakeholders about the project progress or to quickly establish links with actors within the STADIEM consortium and ecosystem. STADIEM partners attended/organised in total between October 2022 and September 2023 24 conferences, workshops or events.

TABLE 1: OVERVIEW OF THE COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES IN YEAR 3 AND OVER 36 MONTHS FOR THE INFORM STAKEHOLDER GROUP

Stakeholder group: inform				
Planned Activities	Planned KPIs	Completed activities/ KPIs in Y3 (Oct '22- Sept '23)	Partners involved	Total Project Score on KPI (Y1 to Y3 cumulative score)
STADIEM website	>1500 unique visitors per month	unique visitors in year 3: 2400	MAR	unique visitors since inception: Y1: 1500 visitors Y2: 12900 visitors Y3: 15300 visitors
STADIEM promotional videos	4 videos per year 100 views per video	Number Video STADIEM channels: 12 videos Total views on STADIEM channels: YouTube: >400 views X/Twitter & LinkedIn: over 6k impressions Video Partner channels: VRT Sandbox: 9 videos All partners: Reshare project posts with video on social media	, VRT, MCB, STK, NMA, F6S, EBU	Number Video STADIEM channels: Y1: 6 videos Y2: 24 videos Y3: 36 videos Total views on STADIEM channels: YouTube: Y1: 523 views Y2: 2200 views Y3: >2600 views X/Twitter & LinkedIn: Y1: 300k Y2: 300K Y3: 306k impressions Video Partner Channels: Overall: Y1: 0 videos Y2: 9 videos Y3: 18 videos VRT Sandbox: Y1: 0 videos Y2: 5 videos Y3: 14 videos MCB: Y1: 0 videos Y2: 3 videos Y3: 0 videos STK: Y1: 0 video

				<p>Y2: 1 video Y3: 0 video</p> <p>All partners: reshare project video posts Y1, Y2 and Y2</p>
<p>Communication on social media, such as LinkedIn and Twitter</p>	<p>Twitter: > 300 followers LinkedIn: > 100 followers</p>	<p>STADIEM channels:</p> <p>Twitter: +154 new posts +40 new followers</p> <p>LinkedIn: + > 200 new posts + 131 new followers</p> <p>Average social media following: 630 stakeholders</p> <p>Social media posts by Partners and on their channels:</p> <p>VRT Sandbox: 16 posts on LinkedIn (2319 followers)</p> <p>MCB: 5 posts LinkedIn/X</p> <p>NMA: 14 posts LinkedIn (>2500 followers) 7 post Twitter/X (>2750 followers) 4 on Instagram</p> <p>STK: 1 post on LinkedIn</p>	<p>Martel, VRT, MCB, NMA,STK</p>	<p>STADIEM channels:</p> <p>Twitter: Y1: number not known Y2: 480 posts Y3: 634 posts</p> <p>Y1: 166 followers Y2: 253 followers Y3: 293 followers</p> <p>LinkedIn: Y1: number not known Y2: more than 400 posts Y3: more than 600 posts</p> <p>Y1: 274 followers Y2: 568 followers Y3: 699 followers</p> <p>Average social media following: 630 stakeholders</p> <p>Social Media posts by Partners on their channels:</p> <p>VRT Sandbox: Y2 +Y3: 58 posts on LinkedIn (2319 followers)</p> <p>MCB: Y2+Y3: 41 posts on LinkedIn /X Twitter/FB/Instagram</p> <p>NMA: Y2+Y3: 21 posts LinkedIn (>2500 followers)</p>

				Y2+Y3: 7 post Twitter/X (>2750 followers) Y2+Y3: 4 on Instagram STK: 5 posts on LinkedIn
Word-to-mouth campaigns during industry-networking events	Not applicable	7 STADIEM events Consortium members present at Slush 2022, Big Score 2022, SXSW 2023, Latitude59, MediaCityOdense MediaTech Festival 2023, Future Week 2023, IBC2023 17 other events See also 17 events in 'Convince' section 'engage at workshop/events'.	STK, VRT, MCB, NMA, EBU	STADIEM events: Y1: 0 (impact Covid19) Y2: 4 events Y3: 11 events Other industry-networking events: Y1: 4 other events, but impact Covid-19 Y2: 21 other events Y3: 42 other events

■ 3.2 Results after 3 years of STADIEM

The last column of Table 1 indicates that STADIEM at the end of its 3 years existence managed to achieve most of its communication objectives in order to inform broader audiences about the project's program, scale-ups showcases and increasingly towards the end of the project the concrete outcomes and impacts.

The described partners efforts to publish from year 2 (September 2021) onwards own videos and social media posts (as well as reshare the project posts) complemented in the last two years the efforts via the STADIEM project channel (see the impressions and views) and compensates for the somewhat lower scores regarding Twitter and LinkedIn followers KPIs.

Table 2 shows that besides information via formal online and informal tools, word-of-mouth at networking or industry events was throughout the project an important tool to pass quick updates and message along key stakeholders. A program like STADIEM thus needs community management that is both focused on the online as well as on the real-life dimensions of the task.

The communication actions portrayed here to inform broader stakeholder segments were not exclusive for that segment. They served also the two other stakeholder categories and hence the more specialised audiences of convince and engage segment that the hubs and other three project partners reach via their particular channels and that were employed to support the STADIEM purposes.

4. CONVINCING

In the third year of the project, the stakeholders within the convince segment - non-media sectors/verticals related to the media industry, media producers, traditional media, operators, and researchers in industry and academia/education - not only had to be informed about the existence of the program (for example to reach out to scale-ups in their networks or to act as a pilot) but also about the concrete results and impact of the accelerator program. Convincing the actors in this segment is directed to use STADIEM results (for example to discover innovative solutions that can be further adopted in the media sector or non-media verticals; to discover the STADIEM approach to foster innovation in media or other transfer it to other sectors) and hence to provide wider support for the sustainability work in WP5 and beyond the project by showing the relevance of the project beyond the core group of stakeholders from the media sector itself the 'engage segment'.

■ 4.1 Discussion year 3 activities convince.

To reach that ambition, STADIEM members have participated in various international events and launched specific targeted communication.

- Consortium members were invited 6 times to talk about STADIEM in international settings such as the Future Media Hubs - Sandbox meetings (audience of media corporates, presenting outcomes of program but also impact and future of STADIEM), Future Media Hubs event '*Shaping the future of media: a transatlantic dialogue on innovation*' at SXSW 2023 in Austin (STADIEM presentation showcasing some solution, the program and its role in European media innovation), Kinnermet 2023, Industry Innovation Forum 2022, Latitude59, and EMF Start-ups keynote 2023 (in these three events STADIEM, its program and solution were part of the presentation and contributions by consortium member Storytek to an audience of policy makers, innovators in media & technology and industry leaders).
- Besides these invitations, consortium partners engaged during 16 events with these stakeholders to showcase STADIEM results. While in the invitations STADIEM was often the main topic of the talk/intervention by a STADIEM consortium partner, when engaging at workshops, STADIEM was showcased/introduced as part of a broader presentation. A part of the 16 17 events were also attended in the 2nd year of the project - due to their relevance as a significant meeting place for media innovators, business leaders and policy makers in Europe - but we also see that broader innovation events from the USA and Asia are getting interested in the STADIEM story (SXSW 2023, Taipei city invitation, Busan, ...).
- STADIEM has published 2 press releases in the final year, announcing the selection of scale-ups that made it to the integrate phase and announcing the 4 Pilot events organized by STADIEM where the 6 OC2 pilot solutions were showcased by the beneficiaries. These press releases were sent to contacts within the specialized press. See also D5.9 '*Outreach impact creation activities report v2*' for more information about the press release and press activities of STADIEM.
- Consortium partners have contributed to amplifying the project's communication through specific targeted publications:
 - a tech-I issue by the EBU in September 2023 for (public) media about the 6 pilots in OC2.

- LinkedIn posts on VRT Sandbox and internal website company about the work of 3 scale-ups targeting scale-ups, business leaders, investors and innovators in Flanders, Belgium, and Europe.
- STADIEM digital book about the accelerator work by Storytek to 300 relevant stakeholders in the EU (to be in October 2023)
- Reporting on STADIEM in their newsletters (NMA/MCB providing interviews with scale-ups for which they were a mother hub to their network).

Annex III provides an overview of these targeted publications (magazines, newsletters) for STADIEM's third year with relevant links.

As with the actions in the inform segment, the actions highlighted here are not exclusive targeted to actors the convince segment. Especially given the overall strategy of the third year to focus on results and connect to stakeholders and actors that are important for the project sustainability, actions labelled here (especially the targeted publication) were also used to reach the actors in the engagement segment.

Table 2 below shows that all KPI's were met and this for the 2nd year in a row.

TABLE 2: OVERVIEW OF THE COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES FOR THE 3RD YEAR AND THE PROJECT FOR THE CONVINCING STAKEHOLDER GROUP

STAKEHOLDER GROUP: CONVINCING				
Planned Activities	Planned KPIs	Completed activities/ KPIs in Y3 (Oct '22- Sept '23)	Partners involved	Total Project Score on KPI (Y1 to Y3 cumulative score)
Invitations to participate in workshops /events	At least 6 per year	6 events/workshops 2 Future Media Hubs presentations, SXSW 2023 - FMH event, Latitude59, Industry Innovation Forum 2022, Kinnernet Europe, EFM Startups 2023 keynote	VRT, STK, EBU, NMA, MCB, EBU,	Number of events/workshops Y1: 3 events Y2: 14 events Y3: 20 events
Engage at workshop/ events	At least 6 per year	17 events/workshops Showcasing the findings and promoting the program in the key ecosystem events including: B3 Biennale 2022, Industry Innovation Forum Tallinn 2022,	STK, VRT	Engage at workshops/events Y1: 8 events Y2: 25 events Y3: 52 events

		<p>Geneva Digital Market 2022, Slush 2022, DLD 2023, EFM Start-ups 2023, Future Media Hubs Mission London 2023, Focus Asia 2023, Marche Du Film - Festival de Cannes 2023, Latitude59 2023, Kinnernet Europe 2023, Kinnernord 2023, MTH 2023 conference.</p> <p>Additional showcases: STADIEM findings for Taiwanese ecosystem (invitation by Taipei City, September 2023) Estonian start-up ecosystem players for the development of Estonian start-up ecosystem (August 2023), MTH 2023 conference (September 2023), discussing partnerships and showcasing findings at FLY ASIA start-up ecosystem summit for the Busan City Government (October 2023, South Korea).</p>		
<p>Targeted publications</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>4 publications + 18 via partners STADIEM Project</p> <p>Press releases: 2, distributed via Prowly to 17 contacts in the specialised press</p> <p>Partners: VRT: 2 publications on Linked-In</p>	<p>MAR, VRT, STK</p>	<p>STADIEM Project:</p> <p>Press releases Y1: 4 press releases Y2: 8 press releases Y3: 12 press releases</p> <p>Campaign corporate engagement: Y2: 5 specialist publications</p>

		<p>3 publications: on internal website</p> <p>EBU: Presentation STADIEM and OC2 promotion in Article Tech-i EBU-Magazine; issue 57, September 2023</p> <p>STK: LinkedIn: 2 (1 dedicated publication on STADIEM Accelerator book and 1 dedicated post about STADIEM – under review at time of submission deliverable)</p> <p>NMA: Newsletter items : 9</p> <p>MCB: newsletter items : 4</p>		<p>STADIEM Accelerator book: online via website</p> <p>Project Partners:</p> <p>VRT Sandbox:</p> <p>LinkedIn posts (Y1+Y2+Y3): Internal website VRT (Y1+Y2+Y3): 3</p> <p>EBU: Articles in Tech (Y1: 1x; Y2: 1x; Y3: 1x): 3</p> <p>STK: LinkedIn : 3 post (success story pilot OC1, STADIEM accelerator book + about project (tbc)</p> <p>NMA: Newsletter items: 13</p> <p>MCB: Newsletter items: >6 Website publication: 2</p> <p>F6S: social network : targeted publications on OC1 and OC2</p>
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■ 4.2 Results after three years of STADIEM

Looking at the results in a three-year perspective, one can, based on the KPIs, conclude that STADIEM was successful in attending leading innovation events and workshops in Europe, either on invitation (for example to speak or be an active participant in a workshop) – over 30 events - or by engaging during such an event as part of the broader audience – 52 events. STADIEM partners not only attended most of these events twice or even three times during the project's lifespan, hence being able to inform stakeholders not only about the existence of the program, but also its progress and results. It also allowed to build and deepen connection with the stakeholders. The international events itself were scattered over Europe, covering the Baltics, the Anglo-Saxon world but also France (Cannes).

STADIEM has in practice since its first year used the category of targeted publications for both the actors in the convince segment but and the engage segment. From the angle of the defined KPI for community building, STADIEM also here has been successful. In the first two years for the open calls, actors in the convince segment were useful for helping to feed the program with relevant scale-ups whose technology might be interesting for the media sector. In the 2nd half of the project (from August 2022 onwards), it became important to feed them with insights about accelerator work and new technological solutions emanating from STADIEM OC1 and OC2. Besides the press releases that were more explaining the STADIEM process flow and selection of technologies and scale-ups, the STADIEM newsletters (see also section 5 '*Engage*' and D5.9 'Outreach and impact creation activities report v2') and partner newsletters were focusing increasingly on outcomes and impacts and on success stories of pilot sale-ups. The STADIEM Accelerator Handbook is an important output of the project that is also going to be an inspiration for other non-media verticals looking for ways to foster scale-ups driven innovation. Stakeholders in the convince segment are thus part of an important target communication at the end of the project.

5. ENGAGE

In the final year of the project, the efforts of STADIEM within the engage segment moved from efforts to convince scale-ups to join the STADIEM Innovation program to engage European media corporates, investors and venture capitalists and policy makers in activities that showcased the STADIEM beneficiaries and demonstrated the necessity, value and impact of the first pan-European accelerator program for the media sector. Such activities had to support the sustainability work in WP5 (and reported in D5.7 '*Market analysis, exploitation and sustainability v1*') by connecting consortium partners with interesting actors to design and explore future scenarios for STADIEM but also to allow scale-ups to generate new business and investment leads. In line with the goal set at the end of the 2nd year, STADIEM focused mainly on setting up its own events at international conferences that were not organized by one of its own partners.

■ 5.1 Discussion year 3 activities engage.

In total STADIEM organized between October 2022 and September 2023 over the Europe Union 11 different types of events (workshops, matchmaking events, showcasing events, informal networking) to achieve the engagement ambitions:

- Introducing and connecting scale-ups with investors in Europe:
 - STADIEM's Investor Week with 4 scale-ups pitches in the Media track at the Big Score 2022 festival in Gent (Rumble Studio, Trensition, Tinkerlist, Aiconix), 7 scale-ups mingling and having one-on-one meeting with investors and OC1 scale-up Datavillage in the Belgian Track.
 - Two-day visit to Slush 2022 with 3 OC2 scale-ups (Rumble, Scriptix and Bottalk) with guidance and introduction by 4 hub representatives (MCB, VRT Sandbox, NMA and STK) to various actors.
- Introducing OC2 pilot scale-ups to media corporates during a special matchmaking session at Media City Odense in May 2023 and an informal mingling event (happy hour) at Future Week 2023 in Bergen at MCB HQ in June 2023.
- 4 Showcasing event of the OC2 pilots towards an audience of corporates, companies and investors at main stages of Latitude59, Media City Odense MediaTech Festival and Future Week and on the presentation stage at the EBU stand at IBC2023 in September 2023
- 3 STADIEM workshops for scale-ups, investors and corporates at Latitude59 in May 2023, for European policy makers in Brussels in September 2023, for technology departments of European media companies at Production Technology Seminar 2023 in Geneva at EBU HQ in January 2023
- STADIEM demos by 3 Integrate OC2 beneficiaries to AI & Data experts of European Media companies at Data Technology Seminar in Geneva at EBU HQ in March 2023
- STADIEM roundtables with investors in July 2023 to explore the accelerator program and looking for market opportunities/market insights regarding the sustainability scenarios for the STADIEM accelerator.

The participation of STADIEM members in events and the events organised by STADIEM was promoted through STADIEM's communication channels (website and social media) and the (online/social) networks of Martel and other STADIEM partners (see also section 3 on 'inform' in this deliverable and for more details D5.9 '*Outreach and impact creation activities report v2*'). Promotional materials, such as pod designs, videos (compilation of scale-up and hubs testimonials, match event videos, pitches recordings and open call video), and brochures, were

produced to support the engagement of stakeholders during these events.

Besides connecting scale-ups with other ecosystems and investor and media stakeholders by means of the events mentioned above, STADIEM partners also continued to facilitate the integration of the scale-ups into their own local ecosystems. For Media City Bergen its Future Week Festival served as a vehicle to integrate the pilots in its own ecosystem, while the VRT and NMA used the Sandbox Hub as a channel to keep European media corporates informed about the progress of the project and the beneficiaries. Finally, Storytek organised in March 2023 at the beginning of the Integrate Phase a two-day bootcamp that introduced the 12-remaining scale-ups with two growth experts in its network (Sebastien Toupy & Guido Van Nispen). Besides insights on the scaling and growth process, the 12 scale-ups could present their case and got practical tips during a one-on-one meeting.

As part of the overarching communication strategy in the last year to focus more on outputs and impacts of STADIEM on the media sector and on the innovators (scale-ups), in particular towards the stakeholders in the engagement segment, the consortium focused on presenting success stories from the 10 pilot scale-ups of the two cohorts. A special booklet for IBC 2023, published on the STADIEM website, highlighted not only the impact of STADIEM but also gave a page to each of the 10 scale-ups to present their STADIEM solution and relevance on the corporate they worked with and the media industry in Europe at large. Pilot success stories were also the focus of the last newsletters of STADIEM (September 2023), also reinforcing the showcase event and boot of STADIEM at IBC2023. Three partners (VRT, MCB, STK) published their own kind of success stories, focusing on scale-ups that were active in their ecosystem or for which they were playing a role as mother hub (Scriptix - MCB, Limecraft - VRT, FilmChain - STK).

The STADIEM newsletter from December 2023 focused on the one hand on presenting the successful outcomes and results of the program by means of an attractive visual with key figures and on the other hand in announcing STADIEM presentations at important events (PTS2023, SXSW 2023, Latitude59, IBC2023; workshop Brussels 2023) where concrete results of the scale-up to corporate supplier program were highlighted and the need for a framework such as STADIEM for the European media sector was expressed.

Given the status of the Innovation Program in the 3rd year (the 3rd year started with the Develop Phase OC2 ongoing and the Pilot OC1 ending), webinars to promote the program, onboarding meetings and launch events of the program were no longer relevant as action in the third year and are labelled in the table with n/a (not applicable).

TABLE 3: OVERVIEW OF THE COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES FOR THE THIRD YEAR AND THE PROJECT FOR THE ENGAGE STAKEHOLDER GROUP

STAKEHOLDER GROUP: ENGAGE				
Planned Activities	Planned KPIs	Completed activities/ KPIs in Y3 (Oct '22-Sept '23)	Partners involved	Total Project Score on KPI (Y1 to Y3 cumulative score)
Webinars to promote the programme	2 per open call	n/a	n/a	Number of webinars: Y1: 2 webinars OC1 (160 participants)

				Y2: 4 webinars OC1 and OC2 (81 participants)
Showcasing and getting together at international events facilitated by the STADIEM network	Not applicable	7 events Slush 2022, Big Score 2022, DTS2023, Latitude59, MediaCityOdense 2023, IBC2023, SXSW2023	STK, NMA, MCB, VRT, EBU, F6S, MARTEL	Number of events Y1: 3 events (online) Y2: 10 events Y3: 18 events
Showcasing and getting together at international events organised by the STADIEM network	Not applicable	3 events Future Week 2023, PTS and DTS 2023	MCB, EBU	Number of events Y1: 4 Y2: 5 Y3: 8
Big Bang proceeding the Match Phase of OC2	1 event	n/a	n/a	Number of Big Bang events Match Phase: Y1: 1 (OC1) Y2: 2 (OC2)
Develop Phase Onboarding OC2	Not applicable	n/a	n/a	Number of onboarding events: Y1: 1 onboarding event Y2: 1 onboarding event
Participation in project-related events	At least 4	5 project related events Workshop 2 PTS 2023, Workshop 3 Latitude59, Workshop 4 Brussels, IBC event 2023	VRT, MCB, F6S, NMA, STK, EBU, F6S, MARTEL	Number of events: Y1: 7 events Y2: 15 events Y3: 20 events
Demo Day at the end of the project	1 Demo Day per open call	5 demo opportunities: Future Week demo day event 2023 and pilo demo showcase (Latitude59 2023, Media City	MCB, VRT, STK, EBU, NMA, F6S, MARTEL	Number of demo events Y1: n/a Y2: 1 demo event Y3: 6 demo events

		Odense 2023, IBC2023)		
Access to and integration in the partner's hub and networks	Not applicable	<p>VRT: Sandbox Hubs updates :2 meetings</p> <p>STK: Stadiem OC2 bootcamp digital webinar on B2B growth and a 2-day mentorship program for STADIEM beneficiaries (with mentors Guido Van Nispen and Sebastien Toupy</p> <p>MCB: Future Week</p>	STK, MCB, VRT	<p>Overview of access given</p> <p>Y1: 4 Match events at hubs (all online)</p> <p>Y2: 4 Match events at hubs (OMR, Innovation Café, Future Week, STK online) + travel</p> <p>Y2+Y3: FMH bi-monthly update</p> <p>Y3: STK bootcamp</p> <p>Y3: MCB Future Week</p>
Videos, interview and success stories online	Not applicable	<p>5 STADIEM newsletters, particular focus on success stories OC2 in last newsletter and on website (+OC1)</p> <p>STADIEM project booklet OC2 IBC 2023</p> <p>2 Vlogs covering the STADIEM "Investors Week" (General video and Big Score reportage) published to YT channel and website (plus additional versions deployed exclusively on social media); Elevator Pitch and Lightning Round brief testimonials series deployed on STADIEM social media channels;</p>		<p>STADIEM Actions</p> <p>STADIEM newsletters: 12 (with success stories OC1 and OC2 in Y3)</p> <p>STADIEM videos: 12 Video Testimonials OC1 Develop Phase beneficiaries and hubs 2 vlogs (Investors Week) Elevator Pitch & Lightning Round Series featuring OC2 Investors Week Participants OC2 beneficiaries</p> <p>STADIEM project booklet: 1 for IBC 2022 (OC1 & OC2 Develop beneficiaries) & IBC 2023 (OC1 and OC2 pilots)</p>

		<p>MCB: * 2 publications on website (Integrate Phase and Scriptix)</p>	<p>Partners actions:</p> <p>VRT Sandbox Matchmaking event at VRT video</p> <p>MCB: MBC Expo 2021 Future week demo event 2022 online on YouTube</p> <p>2 success stories Integrate Phase on website (Scriptix)</p> <p>STK: success story Filmchain on LinkedIn</p>
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■ 5.2 Results after 3 years of STADIEM

Three years of community building towards broader ecosystems of media corporates, investors and scale-ups can be considered a success since all KPIs set have been met 3 years in a row.

The open call and cohort guidance actions (Open Call webinar, Develop Phase Onboarding event, Match Big Bang events) were not only on the level of attendance a success but important to note was that the participants came increasingly from a wider area of Europe (from the Baltics to Ukraine via Spain and Ireland to Scandinavia, Germany and the BENELUX), although South-Eastern Europe remained a challenge to reach. Moreover, the fact that the KPIs were successfully reached also, increased the likelihood that the beneficiaries of the program would have a good experience and would make publicity for the program to their contacts, both relevant for the OC2 in the 2nd year and for sustainability efforts in the final year. In the light of this reasoning are the consistent actions undertaken to integrate the scale-ups in the ecosystem of the hubs – via the specific Match Phase events set up by the hubs as well as the constant information flow about the program via the Sandbox Hub and other matching events – an important achievement during the three years.

What concerns showcasing of scale-ups and demonstrating outcomes and impacts of the program to media actors and investors, STADIEM took initially benefit of online opportunities during COVID-19 but managed to set up a wide range of physical events (organised or facilitated by STADIEM) that increasingly expanded in the last year to industry events that were more loosely connected to the hubs (e.g. MediaTech Festival Media City Odense 2023, Slush 2021 and 2022, SXSW 2023, OMR 2022, TechChill Milano 2022, IBC 2022 and 2023), targeted a specific audience (Big Score 2023, Latitude59, PTS and DTS 2023) and were more spread over Europe (Italy, Belgium, Estonia, Germany, Denmark, Netherlands, Switzerland).

The diversity of opportunities to learn about and engage with STADIEM consortium partners or scale-ups increased. These efforts of course also served the purpose to reach and inform stakeholders from the 'inform' and 'convince' segments and to support the actions towards them.

Finally on the level of dissemination, one can note an increasing diversity of approaches to video to show the many facets of the program – from testimonials to a more behind the scenes or experiences of the program – and again, after communication about the requirements and the process of the two cycles, a growing shift towards new formats in print and digital that allow to portray easily key figures and facts about the relevance, impacts and outputs of STADIEM, supporting the increasing engagement with media actors, investors and policy makers.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

Outcomes year 3

The deliverable gave an overview of the project's community building activities from October 2022 to September 2023 based on the community building strategy that is grouped according to the Inform, Convince, Engage methodology.

The report shows that STADIEM for each of the stakeholder segments met almost all the KPIs to measure the success of its community building activities. The first group ('Inform') was reached mainly through communication and dissemination actions by the project and consortium partners, while the second ('Convince') and third groups ('Engage') were reached through targeted communication, encounters, and events of various sizes and formats to build the STADIEM ecosystem and engage them in the STADIEM community.

The main achievements of the third and final project year are the following:

- Deepening 5 key achievements of the previous year:
 - further increasing the communication output and reach, not only via the STADIEM consortium channels but also via the channels of the hubs and partners.
 - Increase the diversity of formats in print and video to show 'behind the scenes' aspect of the program and to provide key outputs about the project to stakeholders.
 - Keep a high level of targeted publications via newsletters from STADIEM and specific contributions about STADIEM on partners own channels (social media posts, Tech-I magazine EBU, etc).
 - Increase the STADIEM presence at physical events, both with STADIEM related events or generating word-of-mouth via participation in events
 - sustaining a good geographical spread of STADIEM presence across Europe.
- Organizing 3 workshops around Europe to present project results to specific target audiences (PTS – Geneva in January 2023 for media corporates/ Latitude59 in May 2023 for investors and scale-ups and Brussels policy workshop in September 2023 for policy makers).
- Setting up 3 specific events to connect STADIEM beneficiaries with target groups (investors and growth and scaling experts): STADIEM Investors Week (Slush 2022 and Big Score 2022) – Bandcamp Storytek – match event at MediaTechFestival Media City Odense.
- organizing a series of 5 formal showcasing and 2 informal networking events around Europe – PTS 2023, DTS 2023, Latitude59, Media City Odense MediaTech Festival, Future Week 2022, IBC2023.
- STADIEM showcasing or networking events took not only place at conferences hosted by project partners (e.g., Future Week at MCB, PTS at EBU) but increasingly made use of the partners network to organise events at other important international business events to connect the project and its beneficiaries with local and various international ecosystems (Slush, Big Score, OMR, TechChillMilano, Media City Odense, etc).

Looking back at the results for the whole duration of the project (September 2020 - September 2023), three major conclusions can be drawn:

- On the level of the KPI's, almost all have been met every year and the initial strategy did not have to change significantly. Lower performance at the beginning of the project

on some KPIs compared to the final year was due to the Covid-19 situation in Europe, although online events and alternatives to conferences were set up and attended in the first 18 months of STADIEM. The score regarding followers on the social media channels of STADIEM is understandable given the chosen approach of STADIEM to also leverage the communication on partners channels, which was done on a regular manner by the partners and especially the 4 hubs. Nonetheless, STADIEM managed to increase every year the followers its accounts (as well as partners account due to STADIEM).

- The community building activities need a good online and offline interaction. Physical international events are important to reach out to and inform key players from the ecosystem, get new contacts, or deepen existing relations during meetings at STADIEM boots. Online actions merely serve information and recall purposes.
- The actions served the focus area of community building activities during the different stages of the project: in the first 18 months a focus on recruiting actors for the different dimensions of the program (scale-ups for the program, experts for framework building, support and trainings) was the key focus; from the summer of 2022 onwards activities served more showcasing purposes and convincing stakeholders from the convince, inform and engage segments to inform and support the sustainability work.

A look into the future

The STADIEM consortium has managed to create and maintain for 3 years (2020-2023) a broader ecosystem around its start-up to corporate supplier accelerator program to nurture the latter but also to enable a smooth transfer of insights and benefits from the program outcomes to the former.

The strategy to keep this ecosystem community alive after the project is related to both the short term and long-term actions described in the sustainability plan. It will be important that on the short term via the STADIEM channels updates, if available, about a new cycle of STADIEM will be announced. Also as described in D5.9 '*Outreach and impact creation activities report v2*', the STADIEM web domain <https://www.stadiem.eu/> will remain active for at least two years after the project's end, so that the insights collected through STADIEM can be available to other initiatives and/or industry, SMEs, etc. so that parties interested in the field of Next Generation Media in Europe can benefit from the results achieved and connect to potential follow-ups. Martel will be available to keep the website updated and the social media channels active accordingly, if needed.

On the longer term, the project partners will play an important role as well by using their network, contacts, events and communication channels to inform the various STADIEM stakeholders from the established ecosystem about new initiatives, to involve them elaboration of the future STADIEM plans and scenarios but also to reach out to them for more local hub-based initiatives where STADIEM experiences and learnings are integrated in programs with start-ups and scale-ups and ecosystem learnings and contacts can be further nurtured.

ANNEXES

○ ANNEX I: OVERVIEW OF VIDEOS BY PROJECT AND PARTNERS IN YEAR 3

● Project Videos

Partner	date	Title	views (YouTube)	link
STADIEM	November 2023	Surviving investors Week	71	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bmvcrfXAU2g
STADIEM	November 2023	Surviving Investors Week: The Big Score	23	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x_Mbn46IL9o
STADIEM	November 2023	What do you need for Investors Week	released only on X/LinkedIn	https://x.com/STADIEMproject/status/1592552645616861186?s=20
STADIEM	19 November 2023	The Elevator Pitch - LImecraft	released only on X/LinkedIn	https://x.com/STADIEMproject/status/1593915255326908416?s=20
STADIEM	28 November 2023	The Elevator Pitch - Tinkerlist	released only on X/LinkedIn	https://x.com/STADIEMproject/status/1597189380321734656?s=20
STADIEM	06 December 2023	The Elevator Pitch - Trensition	released only on X/LinkedIn	https://x.com/STADIEMproject/status/1600074631360102400?s=20
STADIEM	13 January 2023	The Elevator Pitch - Bottalk	released only on X/LinkedIn	https://x.com/STADIEMproject/status/1613823067331100674?s=20
STADIEM	20 January 2023	The Elevator Pitch - VRT Sandbox (STADIEM hub)	released only on X/LinkedIn	https://x.com/STADIEMproject/status/1616351922516299776?s=20
STADIEM	09 December 2022	The Lightning Round - Trensition	released only on X/LinkedIn	https://x.com/STADIEMproject/status/1601170421000249345?s=20

STADIEM	02 December 2022	The Lightning Round - Tinkerlist	released only on X/LinkedIn	https://x.com/STADIEMproject/status/1598592782813126656?s=20
STADIEM	22 November 2022	The Lightning Round - Limecraft	released only on X/LinkedIn	https://x.com/STADIEMproject/status/1594981685606899713?s=20
STADIEM	17 January 2023	The Lightning Round - Bottalk	released only on X/LinkedIn	https://x.com/STADIEMproject/status/1615331256862142464?s=20
STADIEM	27 January 2023	The Lightning Round - VRT Sandbox (STADIEM hub)	released only on X/LinkedIn	https://x.com/STADIEMproject/status/1618901532652761088?s=20

An additional clip to promote Open Call 2 webinars was created but posted exclusively on social media to be used in the related paid adv campaign (total reach: >220k)

Project partners' videos

Partner	date	title	views (LinkedIn)	link
VRT - Sandbox	Nov 2022	STADIEM Investors Week vlog intro	142	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6998328153404231682
VRT - Sandbox	Nov 2022	Investors Week vlog Day 1	152	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7000446694014214144
VRT - Sandbox	Nov 2022	Investors Week vlog Day 2	142	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7001182353993654272
VRT - Sandbox	Nov 2022	Investors Week vlog Day 3	240	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7001861354705797120
VRT - Sandbox	Nov 2022	Investors Week vlog recap	499	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7003311139354759168
VRT - Sandbox	Dec 2022	Lightning Round with Mother Hub VRT	162	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7009115984254881792

VRT - Sandbox	January 2023	STADIEM Elevator Pitch Bottalk	346	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7020684824084410368
VRT - Sandbox	February 2023	Introducing 12 Integrate Start-ups	611	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7031967179168215041
VRT - Sandbox	May 2023	Introducing 6 Pilot Start-ups	586	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7062078480871518209

○ ANNEX II : COMMUNICATION ON SOCIAL MEDIA BY PROJECT PARTNERS

Besides the 606 posts on Twitter and more than 600 posts on LinkedIn on the STADIEM project social media and curated by communication partner Martel, the 4 hubs have actively communicated on social media about STADIEM via their social media channels.

- **VRT**

VRT Sandbox posted on its LinkedIn Account (2319 followers) 16 posts regarding diverse elements of the Project.

Partner	date	title	link
VRT-Sandbox	6/10/2022	The Big Score announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6983708903955931136
VRT-Sandbox	18/10/2022	The Big Score announcement 2	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6988052859493695488
VRT-Sandbox	7/11/2022	The Big Score announcement 3:	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6995389620746121216
VRT-Sandbox	15/11/2022	STADIEM at Slush	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6998202501107744768
VRT-Sandbox	19/12/2022	OC1 Pilot Trensition at The Big Score	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7010579423317876736
VRT-Sandbox	21/12/2022	OC2 BotTalk pitch at VRT:	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7011358000850288640
VRT-Sandbox	05/01/2023	Tinkerlist collaboration with VRT	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7016795202270973952

VRT - Sandbox	11/01/2023	OC2 Limecraft collaboration with VRT	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7018945736566276096
VRT - Sandbox	12/01/2023	Training Tuesday Recap with Sirris about Internal Scaling	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7019258167532363776
VRT - Sandbox	19/01/2023	STADIEM at PTS EBU	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7021835888980566016
VRT - Sandbox	26/01/2023	STADIEM at SXSW 2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7024335331902550016
VRT - Sandbox	09/02/2023	Progress post OC2 pilot Scriptix	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7029456445494448128
VRT - Sandbox	02/03/2023	VRT Sandbox goes to	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7037006340191322112
VRT - Sandbox	09/03/2023	Tickets FMHs and STADIEM at SXSW 2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7039587897708044288
VRT - Sandbox	16/03/2023	EBU's DTS	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7042075709283950592
VRT Sandbox	25/05/2023	STADIEM at Latitude59	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7067511427976089602

- **MCB**

Over its various social media accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram), MCB has posted 5 messages regarding STADIEM activities

Partner	date	title	link
MCB	November 2022	STADIEM Investors Week	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6988117898577743873
MCB	November 2022	MCB and STADIEM at Slush 2022	https://twitter.com/MediaCityBerg/en/status/1582727990470791169
MCB	November 2022	Big Score 2022	https://twitter.com/MediaCityBerg/en/status/1582352862914711554

MCB	February 2023	STADIEM: Progress report from Scriptix	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7028721998667165696
MCB	February 2023	Check out what Scriptix has been doing with its corporate	https://twitter.com/MediaCityBergen/status/1622959955568390144

- **NMA**

NMA reshared on its LinkedIn channel (over 2500 followers) and Twitter/X channel (over 2750 followers) the various tweets, posts or pictures about STADIEM from the STADIEM accounts, consortium partner accounts and consortium individual collaborators account. NMA posts concerning STADIEM related specifically to scale-ups for which NMA was a motherhub.

Partner	date	title	link
NMA	15/03/2023	Audio Quickies - Rumble	https://x.com/_merlen/status/1636016541215907841?s=20
NMA	13/03/2023	Thumbs up for: IZI Record	https://x.com/NMA_vc/status/1635306851058450433?s=20
NMA	02/02/2023	Develop Phase - Vialog	https://x.com/NMA_vc/status/1621187155790860290?s=20
NMA	30/01/2023	Demo Oragne - IZI Record	https://x.com/NMA_vc/status/1620004436478431233?s=20
NMA	17/11/2022	Bottalk - FMH side event Slush 2022	https://x.com/NMA_vc/status/1593228910841704448?s=20
NMA	20/09/2022	STADIEM meeting - future of media innovation	https://x.com/NMA_vc/status/1572227498657853444?s=20
NMA	November 2022	STADIEM investor week	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/nmavc_stadium-investor-week-full-video-activity-7006278701243850752-fjPp?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
NMA	November 2022	NMA and Tinkerlist	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/nmavc_christoph-h%C3%BCning-managing-partner-at-nma-activity-7011024280431783936-n0wM?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
NMA	December 2022	NMA 2022 review including STADIEM	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/nmavc_startups-innovation-acceleration-activity-7011646730416840704-TZfA?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

NMA	January 2023	Demo Time IZI Records	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/nmavc_accelerator-ai-live-activity-7025774022986461184-pycX?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
NMA	February 2023	Demo Time Vialog	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/nmavc_mediatech-accelerator-video-activity-7026954946491109376-ZIKG?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
NMA	March 2023	Demo Time Rumble Studio	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/nmavc_contentcreation-software-mediatech-activity-7041794226572951552-i9H?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
NMA	15 September 2023	STADIEM at IBC2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7109423344927559680
NMA	October 2022 - September 2023	3 Instagram posts on NMA Instagram Channel: IZI Record, Rumble and Vialog	https://www.instagram.com/reel/Cp0ENNs teeZ/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igshid=MzRIODBiNWFIZA== https://www.instagram.com/reel/CoKpsYw Dkx/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igshid=MzRIODBiNWFIZA== https://www.instagram.com/reel/CoCPI28s afc/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igshid=MzRIODBiNWFIZA

- **STORYTEK**

Storytek communicated via its LinkedIn Channel (3484 followers) 4x times specific on STADIEM activities with its own content creation, besides resharing Stadiem social media project posts.

Partner	date	title	link
STK	January 2022	STADIEM OC2 and tech-i publication STADIEM	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/stensaluvener_stadiem-startup-mediatech-activity-6873558958989209600-4zpU/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
STK	February 2022	STADIEM Open Call 2 promotion	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/stensaluvener_opencall-mediainnovations-incubation-activity-6904062436844933120-goYC/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

STK	June 2022	STADIEM OC2 Promo for Corporate and Investor matches	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/stensaluveer_activity-6939990373763092480-plxC/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
STK	September 2022	OC1 Pilot Case Study: Filmchain	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/stensaluveer_horizoneurope-innovation-startups-activity-7003686274003791872-2DK/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

○ ANNEX III: TARGETED PUBLICATIONS BY STADIEM PARTNERS

Besides the press releases issued by communication Martel and the targeted campaigns by Martel to corporates, the STADIEM partners realised the following articles in (online) magazines and external/internal newsletters:

Partner	date	title	link
VRT	6/12/2022	Interview with Delphine DeWulf: How to score Big Fish	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7005899859274682368
VRT	23/2/2023	23/2/23 Interview with Maarten Verwaest (Limecraft): AI subtitling for Short-form Video via Adobe Panel:	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7034523741606813696
VRT	22/2/203	Automatic subtitling for short form video: do you already use it?	internal website vrt
VRT	23/3/2023	Do you know how a synthetic VRT voice sounds like?	internal website vrt
VRT	April 2023	Ukrainian start-up Wantent uses AI for Homo Universalis program	internal website vrt
EBU	September 2023	Tech i magazine issue 57, p.4: How STADIEM has accelerated media innovation in Europe	https://tech.ebu.ch/docs/tech-i/tech-i-057.pdf
MCB	October 2022 - September 2023	4 features on the Media City Bergen Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/mediacitybergen/4895017-6226135 https://mailchi.mp/mediacitybergen/4895017-6172947 https://25322252.hubspotpreview

			eu1.com/hcms/preview/email/70230230261?portalId=25322252&preview_key=hFUytGUv&preview=true&from_buffer=false&cacheBust=0
STK	September 2023	Key lessons from STADIEM	LinkedIn; under review when submitting the deliverable
STK	4th semester 2023	STADIEM Accelerator Book	Digital form sent to 300 stakeholders
NMA	October 2022 - September 2023	9 features on the NMA newsletter	https://open.substack.com/pub/nmavc/p/nma-monday-alert-25?r=1tuy7j&utm_campaign=post&utm_medium=web https://open.substack.com/pub/nmavc/p/nma-monday-alert-26?r=1tuy7j&utm_campaign=post&utm_medium=web https://open.substack.com/pub/nmavc/p/nma-monday-alert-27?r=1tuy7j&utm_campaign=post&utm_medium=web https://open.substack.com/pub/nmavc/p/nma-monday-alert-11?r=1tuy7j&utm_campaign=post&utm_medium=web https://open.substack.com/pub/nmavc/p/nma-monday-alert-10?r=1tuy7j&utm_campaign=post&utm_medium=web https://open.substack.com/pub/nmavc/p/nma-monday-alert-1?r=1tuy7j&utm_campaign=post&utm_medium=web https://open.substack.com/pub/nmavc/p/nma-monday-alert-12?r=1tuy7j&utm_campaign=post&utm_medium=web https://open.substack.com/pub/nmavc/p/nma-monday-alert-5?r=1tuy7j&utm_campaign=post&utm_medium=web

